

THE ROLE OF THE BOOK IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE STUDENT'S PERSONALITY. THE BOOK IS A SPIRITUAL MASTER

Djurayeva Perdegul Saidovna

National training of teachers of Navai region in new methods center, "Preschool, primary and special educational methods" department associate docent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11082195>

Abstract. *The world of books is the most precious world. The book is the source of our knowledge, our wings for the future, our common sense, a lamp that illuminates our path.*

Keywords: *great thinker, book, law, emotion, human nature, "Five Fingers" method, media safety, informational text, library.*

Introduction

The importance of books and reading cannot be compared in the formation of high spirituality in the hearts of primary school students.

The world of books is the most precious world. This is a universal innovation of human thinking. Its power is to give life to all the dormant emotions in our body. I liken books to corals at the bottom of the ocean. The book is the source of our knowledge, our wings for the future, our common sense, a lamp that illuminates our path. Such descriptions of the book are not free. After all, from "Avesta" to "Past Days", from the well-known "Hamsa" to "Laws of Medicine", even the holy "Quran" has reached us as a book. A book is a light that illuminates the reader's heart, a treasure that enriches the mind, a teacher that leads to the peak of perfection and spiritual perfection. We cannot use the knowledge we have received from this great teacher for the rest of our lives. Undoubtedly, reading enriches our spiritual world and improves our communication culture. It serves to preserve and deeply study the national wealth left by our great ancestors.

The great thinker Alisher Navai says: "The book is a grateful teacher, the main source of knowledge and spiritual growth." That's why our native people revere it as sacred, follow its example and read it with love. In the modern age of information technology, the number of people who read books is decreasing. Everyone finds the information they need on the Internet, uses e-books. It's not bad, but you won't find the pleasure, joy, and excitement that you get from flipping through a book. Our favorite writer Otkir Hashimov writes: "I don't know if you have noticed, but you have a friend whose loyalty is unparalleled. He will talk to you whenever he wants. It teaches you what you don't know. If you get lost, he will show you the right path... This friend's name is the Book!"

Indeed, promotion of national and world literature models, scientific and public guides to students, instilling in their hearts love for high human qualities such as patriotism, virtue, and formation of book reading culture is one of the urgent tasks of today. consists of young people. The book is of great importance in protecting young people from various threats, i.e. religious extremism, terrorism, fanaticism, "mass culture", protecting them from violations and crimes.

Nowadays, the young generation wants to achieve their dreams quickly and easily. They do not like to be patient and move forward gradually. It would be better to look for the root of crime among young people from those aspects. Studies show that the majority of crimes committed

by students are theft and robbery. The main purpose of this behavior is property interest. Attempting to acquire someone else's property through crime is a sign of a person's spiritual weakness. Moreover, today, young people have become slaves to "very important" things like computer games and mobile phones.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev says: "Now it is a very important issue for all of us, the task of spreading reading to our young people and taking our work to a new level aimed at further increasing the love of books and their spiritual immunity." True, we are happy that the younger generation is reading e-books. However, I don't think reading our greatest works electronically, from a screen you've just played a game on, can bring you any pleasure, emotion or excitement. Except, of course, for getting a lot of scientific information from the Internet. After all, the difference between fiction and other art forms is that the events in it take place directly in the reader's mind and heart. The reader imagines the work of art as he wishes, stages it in his imagination, lives in the events. Therefore, while reading a book, one can enjoy aesthetic pleasure and consciously avoid committing a crime. Therefore, it can be clearly said that in the development of the student's personality, it is one of our urgent tasks to form the reading culture of young people, promote national and world literature models, scientific and mass educational tools, instill in their hearts love for high human qualities such as patriotism and virtue. Today, reading in our country has risen to the level of state policy. Decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of January 12, 2017 "On the establishment of a commission for the development of the system of publishing and distribution of book products, promotion and promotion of book reading and reading culture", the Resolution of September 13 "On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publishing and distribution of book products, increase and promote reading and reading culture" shows how important the role of literature and books is in raising the spirit of society.

It is necessary to love the book, which is considered as a source of knowledge, to read it and keep it as the apple of one's eye, to be selective in reading and to know the culture of reading. This important document is an important step towards the consistent implementation of spiritual and educational processes in the country and the promotion of reading culture. For this purpose, competitions such as "Best book of the year", "Most active reader", "Best children's book of the year", "Book-loving family" are regularly held in the country. The organization of the "Young Reader" competition, which is of special interest to all students, and the awarding of the President's car "Spark" to the winners, is an example of the interest in this field.

Let's not get tired of studying and giving gifts to our grateful teachers who decorate our lives with good deeds, enlighten our minds, bless our homes, open the way to our goals, enrich our thoughts, and lead us to spiritual perfection!

The boy is white, white talk,
Unaware of the worlds,
Message without evil,
Give the child a book!

Research materials and methodology

Stage 1: "Five fingers" method: Analysis of informational text includes 5 important issues such as - Topic - Main idea - Information 1 - Information 2 - Information 3 - Information. Grade 4 Mother Tongue and Literacy New Generation Textbook Part 2 Unit 10 Media Safety. Week 32 Lesson 1 Based on the text "Two Results at Once" (pages 133-134), this method can be covered as a team in the following 1-hour informational text.

Two results at once

Shahlo came to school in a hurry because the first lesson was computer science, which he loved. The teacher started the lesson:

- Dear students, today we will talk with you about the advantages of the Internet. First of all, the Internet has become a part of our future. Therefore, it is very important to learn it well and be able to use it freely. Have you heard about the benefits of using internet networks?

Humor:

- Through the Internet, we can find new friends, we can communicate with our distant peers, - he said.

Teacher:

- In addition, the Internet provides constant communication. Through it, your parents can learn about you. Jahangir, sitting at the last desk, explained that you can easily communicate with your distant relatives.

- For example, my brother studies abroad. My brother and I meet and talk online. The teacher was pleased with his answer and continued:

- In short, we should learn to use the Internet today. Being able to use the Internet freely will also help you get a good job in the future. That's why we're going to talk to you about its features today.

- Children, tell me about those who use the Internet inappropriately, have you heard - the teacher turned to the students. Then Shakir:

- Yes, I heard. Some children only understand computer games through the Internet. The teacher continued to tell the students that there are many opportunities on the Internet:

- Now all of you can find more than 2 interesting information on the topic you are interested in on the Internet.

Students sat down in front of the computer, put on their headphones and began to search for information on the Internet with all their efforts. The teacher sat down so as not to divide their opinion. Having completed the task, Shahlo raised his hand. The teacher was pleased with Shahlo's work and rated it as very good. To Shahlo's teacher:

- You know, teacher, I got a lot of great information while writing the assignment. As you said, if we use the Internet effectively, our knowledge will increase, he said excitedly.

All the students in the class started to give the task. Debates flared up. They were so interested in the lesson that they lost track of time.

Search results

Educational standard for the subject "Native language and reading literacy": informational text and graphics corresponding to the 4th grade level in terms of comprehension factor, taking into account the requirements of listening comprehension, speaking, reading, writing, linguistic education. competence (diagram, table, map, etc.) answers and proves questions about people, places, events and facts when clearly stated (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.5); Grade 4 identifies sentences that convey the main idea or meaning of the text when the information in the text is clearly presented and justifies the answer (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.6); According to the level of the 4th grade, in an informational text, people describe the reasons for their behavior, places, sequence of main events and their causes, problems, solutions, facts, draw conclusions, prove their answers (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O 'Q.A.8); compares and contrasts two characters, describes the relationship between them; offers a suitable way for the behavior of heroes

(O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.9); Determines the topic, purpose and main idea of an informative text corresponding to the level of 4th grade and justifies the answer; determines the author's attitude towards the text, paying attention to the tone of the text (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.11); compares the development, location, time, and actions of the characters in the news text and information text taken from the Internet, draws conclusions and proves their opinions (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.15); responds to texts taken from the Internet with printed text according to the level of 4th grade (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.16); Determines the extent to which content, structure, features, and graphic elements influence finding and understanding information in print text according to grade 4 level (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.17); online media, advertising, and informational text appropriate for grade 4, who is it for, the author's point of view, the purpose and meaning of the text, makes a conclusion to determine its credibility and justifies the answer. (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.18).

After reading the content of the text, the teacher interprets and visualizes it through reading comprehension, the given information is based on the idea of the method, and the learning process continues in an analytical spirit. Summarizing from the content of the topic, the pros and cons of using the Internet depend on the question-and-answer after the teacher's speech, and on the way the small group members read the sequenced text, and on their visual description skills. The main idea of this text is about the effective use of the Internet and the factors in its scope depending on the age of the child.

The teacher's close connection of text content with real life events serves to ensure a positive result; The ability to find appropriate sentences from the text as 1-3 data, connect them in a meaningful and logical way, identify new words or phrases, creates a basis for small studies and research in students. Students will be able to easily find the necessary material from any source, distinguish sentences within the limits of their intelligence. It allows to form the ability to search, find and place information in algorithmic order from non-textual sources, i.e. pictures, diagrams, drawings.

It is important to understand what the main idea of these sources is. Because being able to influence the content of the text means regulating students' thoughts and this is the main goal of the lesson. After analyzing the text, learning the meaning, explanation and synonyms of some words in the informational text, writing tasks in oral and written speech are performed. On this text, the pictures provided in the textbook, predictable thoughts, silent reading of the text, paying special attention to the use of new words, development of events, recalling heroes, etc. Strengthening the skills of understanding the text through questions and answers helps students to freely and independently express their thoughts on the text, using examples from life.

It is important to understand what the main idea of these sources is. Because being able to influence the content of the text means regulating students' thoughts and this is the main goal of the lesson. After analyzing the text, learning the meaning, explanation and synonyms of some words in the informational text, writing tasks in oral and written speech are performed. On this text, the pictures provided in the textbook, predictable thoughts, silent reading of the text, paying special attention to the use of new words, development of events, recalling heroes, etc. Strengthening the skills of understanding the text through questions and answers helps students to freely and independently express their thoughts on the text, using examples from life. What do you want to use the Internet for? It is important not to forget the possibilities of saying words with a rich vocabulary, such as the rational use of information and communication sources, media world, the concept of media culture, information security, based on the information that children have

seen or heard. Based on the received information, the teacher should evaluate and praise the students according to the evaluation criteria. As a part of the subject, he can give an assignment as required in the textbook, or he can give an additional assignment as homework.

Discussions. 2-stage "Five fingers" method. Information text analysis

Talent can also be discovered among children with special needs

Israel was diagnosed with ZPR autism. Israel's parents made everything possible for their child to get an education. Israel knows Uzbek, Russian, Arabic and English. He stutters only when he speaks. He always sits in the classroom with his tutor. True, Israel is different from its healthy peers. Then he screams and makes some sounds. According to his mother, Israel becomes aggressive when the weather changes. But the child's ability to draw and choose colors is well developed. He knows the math. Recognizes letters. He only has difficulty reading with syllables. Now you can train with Israel for three to four hours. She is compatible with her peers. It's hard to talk to them, but he tries.

Muhammadhan, who has Down syndrome, is highly educated. Can fully communicate with students. In the past, Muhammadhan used a lot of black color in his paintings. Now there are positive changes in his psyche. He is not shy, does not hesitate and behaves freely in front of the team. He thinks like an adult. Like all children, he sits quietly and tries to answer questions. Readers love this "sunny boy" very much.

THE SEVENTH WORD

When a young child is born from a mother, it is born with two different personalities: one is to drink, eat, sleep. These are the passions of the flesh; without them the body cannot be a hotel for the soul. And it does not grow, it does not gain energy. One is that I wish I knew. If he saw something shiny, he tried it, he was interested in it, he put it in his mouth, he tasted it, he looked at his throat, his face, if there was a trumpet, he sought its voice, even if the dog barked, the cattle roared, someone laughed, someone Even if he is crying, he stands up and runs, "What is it?", "What is this?" and said, "Why is he wheezing?" and said, "Why does this matter?" asking everything he sees and hears, he does not find peace. All this is passion, I want to know, I want to see, I want to learn.

If you don't know all the visible and invisible secrets of the world, at least physically, you will not have a place with humanity. If he does not know it, that soul will not be a human soul, but an animal soul. In the past, God created a human soul out of an animal and created it by showing that effect. "What is this, what is that?" When we say, I wish I could ask something, why don't we put our passion, which leaves us with sleep and food, when we grow up, when our mind comes in, we search for a place, ask for a person, and find science?

We must have expanded our field, increased our treasure, which we passionately gathered, it was food for the soul. The soul was better than the body, and the body should have bowed to the soul. No, we didn't do that. The soul is ruling us in our youth. After he grew up and gained strength, we did not let him go. We paid attention to the soul and body, we did not look at anything with our heart, we did not look at it with our eyes, we did not believe it. We are tired of seeing the outside of what we see with our eyes. We did not think about how the secret will be, we say what happened to the person who did not know it. Even if someone says he left, we don't care. When someone gives advice: "Oh, my God, who is better than who?" - we say, we don't know more, we don't listen.

There is no light in the chest, no faith in the heart. What is better than our animals seen with naked eyes? On the other hand, we are better in our childhood days. Whether we know it or not, we are the children of people who want to know. Today we are worse than animals. The animal does not know, does not claim to know. When we argue that we do not know anything, and we do not give our ignorance to knowledge, we do not know whether we are alive or dead, and we lose our roots. 1891

One of the first ways to get knowledge is to read books. The book teaches life and its laws of struggle. It turns into a person who is wise, resourceful in conversation, and responds immediately. Learning the right lesson from the book leads a person to perfection. Reading also means creating one's thoughts. Books written in an uplifting spirit are very important in raising children.

There is no better friend in the world than a book.

May he be your guardian, he is always by your side.

Be alone with him, he will not hurt you.

One hundred unique pleasures to your soul! (Abdurrahman Jami)

Conclusion. I am grateful to the book for all its good qualities. (M. Gorky)

Love for books, appreciation of them, desire to read books is embedded in the blood of our people. Our people are rightly proud of rare educational materials and literature related to science, literature, and art. In any famous library of the world, you can see the works of calligraphers and artists who gave eternal life to the manuscripts of great scientists and sages who created a treasure of thought. XIX According to N. Khanikov, who got acquainted with the activities of Bukhara madrasas in the middle of the 19th century, a student had to read about 137 books to complete the full course of the madrasa. Our ancestors kept the book like the apple of the eye. They did not wrap anything in the pages of the book. The place where books are stored, whether it is a library or a home, is considered sacred, any book is placed in the cleanest, highest place - on the shelves. Our ancestors used to read the works of Mashrab, Nauai, Bedil and other writers with interest at home. Children participated in the study club. As a result, children's desire to read books increases.

Now the family pays less attention to reading. Parents are busy with work, so they don't have enough time to read with their children in the evening. In the family, it is advisable to allocate a separate room for children and, of course, organize a small bookshelf. At this point, our honorable parents should teach their children that the book is sacred and should be treated with care. In the family, the role of parents and teachers in awakening the child's interest in books and increasing his attention is unparalleled. Interest and love for books should be awakened in the child's heart at a young age, and books should always be loved, respected, cherished and worked with books. From the age of 3-5, parents can use books with colorful pictures "Paint it yourself", "Can you draw?", "Think logically!" should give books. They should buy books-albums that are simple in terms of content, psychologically suitable for their age.

It is better to continue these good works in primary education and to open small libraries in grades 1-4, taking into account age characteristics. Since the development of literacy in general education schools starts from primary grades, it is important to stabilize learning activities in them, to teach reading from an early age. For this, it is appropriate to create a "Class Library" at the initiative of class leaders. According to the self-management system, the number of books in the class and its condition are strictly controlled by appointing the smartest and most educated student as the "Class Librarian". It is important for the class teacher to increase the love of his educated,

talented and talented students for the book and make them love it. Since children believe in miracles, if the heroes of the book get their first impression of them from the tales and legends they heard from their grandparents, parents, educators, and teachers, their knowledge expands by reading the book themselves. The poet Hamid Olimjon also recalls hearing fairy tales and sagas from his grandmother in the epic "Semurg or Parizod and Bunyod". As we said above, the formation and development of students' learning skills depends on the teacher's skills. Reading should be made a necessity. If our children do not have the desire to read, it will be difficult to change their focus on reading. It is not necessary to force them to read, but to arouse their desire to read books. In this regard, it is necessary to directly help parents, teachers, library staff. Children's age and interest should be taken into account. The Italian writer Seneca said: "It is not the quantity of books, but their quality that is useful." Just as a bird cannot fly without two wings, a person cannot understand the truth without learning and connecting the knowledge he has received with each other. We conclude the lesson by summarizing the topics related to teaching and the importance of developing social-emotional skills, based on the textbooks "Mother language and reading literacy". As you work through the curriculum textbook, try to explain the idea that understanding and practicing reading skills can lead to healthy relationships, improved self-esteem, and overall well-being for children.

Tip: Don't forget to practice reading skills every day at home and at school in the subjects you teach! Always be honest with parents and gently explain and explain about their children first by expressing the positive aspects of their achievements, learning conditions and educational characteristics! Based on a psychological approach, celebrate your participation as a coordinated task to overcome the student's negative aspects together! Invite parents to your classes so they can see and appreciate their child's true attitude towards learning and competence! However, every modern teacher should always be ready to demonstrate his professional ethics and tactical qualities at the level of high culture, sharp knowledge, deep intelligence and perfect spirituality.

Because our next-generation textbooks require the development of 4K models to improve our relevant modern knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies and educational activities in the development of 21st century skills. In conclusion, the main part of education is to create a favorable environment for children to learn and learn!

REFERENCES

1. His language and reading literacy. 4th grade Teacher's manual. T.-2023
 2. Johnson D.J. The taste of children's literature. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt Pub, Boston, 2009.
 3. Norton, Donna E., Sandra E. Norton and Amy A. McClure. In terms of children: an introduction to children's literature. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill, 1999.
- Internet sources:
4. Carol Hurst's website for children's literature: <https://www.cfrolhurst.com/>
 5. Reading Roskets. <https://www.readingrockets.org/> What is interactive reading aloud? <https://fpblog.fountasandpinnell.com/what-is-interactive-read-alou>
 6. Readwritethink. <https://www.readwritethink.org/classroom-resources/lesson-plans/infering-characters-change>
 7. ReadWorks. <https://www.readworks.org/>
 8. <https://www.freepik.com> images manbasi.